

Triterpenoids of Indian Dilleniaceae

SIPRA DAN and S. S. DAN

Botanical Survey of India, Calcutta-700 016

Manuscript received 25 May 1979, revised 2 February 1980,
accepted 9 April 1980

In consideration of previous work¹⁻⁴ and our taxonomic interest in the family Dilleniaceae we have examined the leaves of all the twelve indigenous species of Dilleniaceae⁵ with the aim of isolating and identifying the triterpenes and sterols. Table 1 summarizes our findings, which show that

$[\alpha]_D^{+43}$ (CHCl₃). β -sitosterol crystallised from methanol, m.p. 136-137°, $[\alpha]_D^{-35}$ (CHCl₃), acetate, m.p. 126-127°, $[\alpha]_D^{-35}$ (CHCl₃).

Acknowledgement

The authors thank Dr. S. K. Jain, Director, Botanical Survey of India, Howrah-3 for providing facilities. We record our thanks to Dr. S. C. Pakrashi, Deputy Director, Indian Institute of Experimental Medicine, Calcutta-32 for rotation and IR spectra.

TABLE 1—COMPOUNDS ISOLATED FROM DILLENACEAE SPECIES (PERCENTAGE YIELD/DRY WT).

Name of the species	betulinic acid	betulin	lupeol	β -sitosterol
<i>Acrotrema arnothianum</i> Wight	0.53	0.065	0.03	0.019
<i>Dillenia andamanica</i> Parkinson	0.50	0.082	0.02	0.015
<i>D. aurea</i> Smith	0.72	0.045	0.09	0.025
<i>D. bracteata</i> Wight	0.58	0.070	0.08	0.016
<i>D. indica</i> Linn	0.60	0.105	0.015	0.012
<i>D. pentagyna</i> Roxb.	0.98	0.150	0.01	0.010
<i>D. retusa</i> Thunb.	0.85	0.068	0.008	0.006
<i>D. scabralla</i> (D. Don) Roxb. exWall	0.575	0.120	0.032	0.022
<i>Tetracera akara</i> (Burm.f.) Merr.	1.05	0.045	0.045	0.005
<i>T. indica</i> (Houtt. ex Christm. & Panz., Merr.)	0.60	0.01	0.014	0.030
<i>T. sarmentosa</i> (L.) Vahl. subsp. andamanica (Hoogl.) Hoogl.	1.23	0.070	0.006	0.004
<i>T. scandens</i> (L.) Merr.	1.35	0.030	0.005	0.001

besides the widely distributed β -sitosterol, triterpenes of the lupene series viz., lupeol, betulin and butulinic acid occur in all the twelve species examined.

Experimental

Air dried and milled leaves were extracted with hot rectified spirit for 30 hrs. The semisolid mass obtained on evaporation of solvent was triturated exhaustively with ether. Ether insoluble residue being negligible was discarded. From ether soluble portion the triterpenes and sterol were isolated by chromatography over silica-gel and preparative tlc. The triterpenoids and sterol were identified by direct comparison with authentic samples⁶ (tlc, mmp, ir) and preparation of derivatives.

Betulinic acid crystallised from methanol, m.p. 306-309°, $[\alpha]_D^{+6}$ (Ethanol). On treatment with diazomethane methyl betulinate was obtained, crystallised from methanol, m.p. 222-224°. The methyl ester yielded acetate with pyridine-Ac₂O. It was crystallised from ethanol, m.p. 198-201°, $[\alpha]_D^{+20}$ (CHCl₃). Betulin crystallised from benzene-methanol m.p. 252-254°, $[\alpha]_D^{+19}$ (CHCl₃). Acetate prepared, as above, crystallised from methanol, m.p. 220-224°, $[\alpha]_D^{+21}$ (CHCl₃). Lupeol crystallised from ethanol, m.p. 210-212°, $[\alpha]_D^{+22}$ (CHCl₃). Acetate crystallised from ethanol m.p. 209-212°,

References

- S. S. DAN, N. R. MONDAL and SIPRA DAN, *Bull. bot. Surv. India*, 1978, 20, 117.
- G. PAVANASIVAM and M. U. S. SULTANBAWA, *Phytochem.*, 1974, 13, 2002.
- NILIMA BANERJI, P. MAJUMDER and N. L. DUTTA, *Phytochem.*, 1975, 14, 1447.
- E. C. BATE-SMITH and J. B. HARBORNE, *Phytochem.*, 1971, 10, 1055.
- N. C. MAJUMDAR, *Flora of India*, II fascicle, July 1979.
- S. C. PAKRASHI, J. BHATTACHARYYA, SIPRA MOOKERJEE, T. B. SAMANTA and H. VERBRUGGEN, *Phytochem.*, 1968, 7, 461.

Chemical Examination of Essential Oil of *Lantana orangemene*

R. K. BASLAS* and PRADEEP KUMAR

Research Laboratory, Department of Chemistry, Govt.
Raza P. G. College (Rohilkhand University),
Rampur-244 901 (U.P.)

Manuscript received 17 August 1979, revised 17 March 1980,
accepted 9 April 1980

The genus *Lantana* (Fam-Verbenaceae) has about 50 species mostly American, grown in tropical and sub-tropical regions¹. Only few species of *Lantana* are found to grow in Rohilkhand region of U. P. *Lantana orangemene* (flower orange) appears to be very much related to *Lantana camara*, botanically.